

Tsallis Entropy is No Longer Linked To Maximum Probability if $q \neq 1$? Part 4

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In Part 1-3, we argued that Tsallis entropy is not linked with the maximization of probability of N trials using either $p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i)^q$ (which appears in a physical a priori constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)^q = 1$). Rather, it follows from: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i)^q d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \text{constant}$ with $q=1$ yielding $F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i))$. This approach is warranted for $q=1$, but it is not clear why it should be justified for $q>1$.

Here, we note that the above Tsallis approach is consistent with the maximization of N trials using the following probability $G(p(e_i))$ such that: $\ln\{G(p(e_i))\} = F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. In the Tsallis case, $F(p(e_i)) = \ln q(p(e_i)) = \{p(e_i)^q - 1\} / (1-q)$. In such a case: $G(p(e_i)) = \exp\{\ln q(p(e_i))\}$. In other words, it is neither $p(e_i)$ nor $p(e_i)^q$ which is maximized, but rather $G(p(e_i))$ and it is not clear what $G(p(e_i))$ represents physically. It is known that in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, there is also a $G(p(e_i))$ which is maximized, but in these cases G is based on a priori physical considerations and one does not obtain it through $p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) \ln(G(p(e_i))) = 1$.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

As noted in Parts 1-3, Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ follows from:

$$\ln\{\text{Probability of } N \text{ trials}\} = \ln\{\text{Product over } i p(e_i)^N\} \quad ((1))$$

((1)) holds for $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. Maximizing ((1)) subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Hence:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ is linked with maximizing Probability over } N \text{ trials} \quad ((2))$$

In Part 3, we showed that an equivalent condition in this case is:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ and } p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = 1 \rightarrow F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

Condition ((3)) may be applied to the Tsallis case with:

$$p(e_i)^q d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = 1 \quad ((4)) \text{ For } q=1, F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((5))$$

In such a case, there is no sense of maximizing a probability of N trials using $p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i)^q$ as argued in Parts 1-3.

Maximization of $G(p(e_i))$

Here we note that there is in fact a function of probability which takes the place of $p(e_i)$ in the Shannon case, namely $G(p(e_i))$ such that for the Tsallis case:

$$\ln(G(p(e_i))) = \ln_q(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{with } \ln_q(p(e_i)) = \{1 - p(e_i)^q\} / \{1 - q\} \quad ((6))$$

In such a case,

$$G(p(e_i)) = \exp(\ln_q(p(e_i))) \quad ((7))$$

$G(p(e_i))$ plays the role of the $p(e_i)$ in a Shannon scheme, i.e. Product over i $G(p(e_i))$ power $\{NG(p(e_i))\}$ = Probability of N trials.

The issue is that it is not clear why one would create such a $G(p(e_i))$ probability a priori. It seems that it imposes a certain type of interaction on $p(e_i)$ values, so we wish to investigate it further.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Distributions

The notion of $G(p(e_i))$ appears in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, but follows directly from physical conditions. In particular, in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the probability balance reaction is:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((8a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((8b))$$

$((8b))$ implies that if a particle with energy e_1 and another with e_2 are present together, they will automatically interact without any enhancement or hindrance. Physically, however, this is not the situation in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, but this is known a priori, and one may write instead of $((8b))$:

$$\text{Fermi-Dirac} \quad p(e_1)(1-p(e_3))p(e_2)(1-p(e_4)) = p(e_3)(1-p(e_1))p(e_4)(1-p(e_2)) \quad ((9))$$

In this case, the presence of e_1 does not guarantee that it may be converted to e_3 . This only happens if the e_3 level is empty, etc.

In the Bose-Einstein case, there is enhancement:

$$p(e_1)(1+p(e_3))p(e_2)(1+p(e_4)) = p(e_3)(1+p(e_1))p(e_4)(1+p(e_2)) \quad ((10))$$

As a result, what appears as a probability $p(e_i)$ in Shannon's related Probability of N trials = Product over i $p(e_i)$ power $(Np(e_i))$ has $p(e_i)$ replaced with:

$G(p(e_i))$ where $G(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) / \{1 - p(e_i)\}$ Fermi-Dirac and

$$G(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) / \{ 1+p(e_i) \} \text{ Bose-Einstein} \quad ((11))$$

The key point, as noted, is that $G(p(e_i))$ is known a priori based on physical considerations.

Examination of the Tsallis $G(p(e_i))$

((7)) simply yields a probability which is consistent with conservation of e_i . In other words, e_i is an a priori conserved quantity in the problem and $p(e_i)$ as well as $G(p(e_i))$ are strictly functions of this variable. The fact that $p(e_i)$ is present and $p(e_i)$ power q is used in the a priori constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$ power q does not mean that either of these behave like $G(p(e_i))$ from the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac scenarios. The fact that one has ((7)) seems to imply that interactions occur leading to the form $G(p(e_i))$ ((7)) which is essentially the same for all cases, i.e.

$$G(p(e_i)) = \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((12))$$

In other words, the basic Maxwell-Boltzmann factor ((12)) is present for the Fermi-Dirac, Bose-Einstein and Tsallis cases, it is just the form of $G(p(e_i))$ which changes. A key difference with the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases and the Tsallis one is that for the first two, the constraints are:

$\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ ((13)) while for the Tsallis case, one has:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E_{\text{total}} \text{ and } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((14))$$

As a result, in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein scenarios, one introduces $G(p(e_i))$ a priori and then uses:

$$\ln(G(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T \quad ((15))$$

One does not use: $p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} \ln(G(p(e_i))) = 1$ to obtain G as in the Tsallis case for which:

$$p(e_i)^q \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} \ln_q(p(e_i)) = 1 \quad ((16)) \text{ yields the form of } \ln_q(p(e_i)) \text{ with } \ln(G(p(e_i))) = \ln_q(p(e_i)).$$

Thus, there is a fundamental difference between the Tsallis approach and that of the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein situations. ((16)) is a special scenario which mimics that of the Maxwell-Boltzmann situation, but now with the first $p(e_i)$ factor changed to $p(e_i)$ power q and $\ln(p(e_i))$ changed to $\ln_q(p(e_i))$ to deal with this $p(e_i)$ power q factor. One could write instead of ((16)):

$$p(e_i)^q \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} \ln(G(p(e_i))) = 1 \quad ((17))$$

In such a case, one imagines the presence of an interaction such that:

$$\ln(G(p(e_1))) \ln(G(p(e_2))) = \ln(G(p(e_1) G(p(e_2))) \quad ((18))$$

In the case of the a sunflower seed, $p(e_i)$ is the probability that it is not eaten by birds in a day in region i and $p(e_i)$ power q is the power it is not eaten in region i in q days, the time which it takes to germinate. $G(p(e_i))$ on the other hand is ((7)) which is an unusual quantity and does not seem to immediately arise a priori. If it did, then one could simply use $\ln(G(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ to solve the problem as in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases.

In the case of germinating seeds, one may ask: Where is the interaction? If $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and if one considers a variational problem, one must allow for $\delta\{p(e_i)\}$. This implies an adjustment of $p(e_i)$ in one region correlated to changes in other regions. In other words, there is some kind of interaction which occurs. It is $G(p(e_i))$, however, which is the new probability which behaves like $p(e_i)$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and this is strictly imposed by ((17)) which may seem unusual.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Parts 1-3 we argued that the Tsallis approach does not seem to be linked with maximizing overall probability of N trials for either $p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i)$ power q . We suggested that ((4)) seems to be the key statistical principle involved instead. Here we note that there is in fact a probability which behaves like $p(e_i)$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (Shannon) case, namely $G(p(e_i))$ such that $\ln\{G(p(e_i))\} = \ln q(p(e_i))$. Such a $G(p(e_i))$ appears in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein scenarios, but is created from the physical conditions of interactions. In the Tsallis case, $G(p(e_i))$ emerges from the condition ((4)) which is a different approach to statistical mechanics. A priori it seems that one would not guess the form of $\ln q$ or $\exp q$ Tsallis.